

**“SOVEREIGNTY” IN MODERN SOUTH ASIAN ISLAMIC
POLITICAL THOUGHT: CONNOTATION FROM MAUDUDI,
HIFZURRAHMAN SEOHARVI AND ALI MIYA NADWI**

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Abstract

Sovereignty in Islam is one of the controversial and contested ideas in Islam. In the context of its location and possession, Islamists, like Mawdudi preferred God as the Sovereign (*Hakimiyah*). In the classical period of Islam, this controversy got an edge who is the sovereign either God or the people? But, what does it mean if God is sovereign? Is it God who rules over people's life and his interference is axiomatic in every critical sector of people's worldly life? And to what extent people's reason is permitted to endorse God's will? Undoubtedly, it was Maulana Mawdudi who prepared a base for establishing an Islamic state by placing an overemphasis on divine sovereignty, in the wake of colonial ascendancy he declared to establish the *hakimiyah* (divine sovereignty) as one of the necessary conditions to get back the flourishing days of Muslims, as he considered the existing time parallel to him is the time of *Jahiliya* (state or time before the advent of Islamic Arabia), similarly followed by Syed Qutb. However, objections made by scholars such as Ali Miya Nadwi and Hifzurrahman Seoharvi over the explanation of Divine sovereignty by Mawlana Mawdudi need attention. So, the paper will try to fix the transforming thought of Islamist sovereignty via popular sovereignty, because this change has a crucial normative contribution to the understanding of Islamist thought on democracy.

Keywords: Sovereignty of God (*Hakimiyah*), Islamists, Sovereignty of Ummah,

Introduction

In various times and contexts, Islamist political theory has been rife with debates about sovereignty. It began after the death of Prophet

Mohammad (PBUH) in 632 and continued under the rule of four righteous Caliphs, as well as Islamic dynasties and empires. It, however, became highly contentious when Muslim-majority countries began to adopt modern nation-states. The dilemma of whether to recognize the nation-state's popular sovereignty or how to reconcile the essence of popular sovereignty with Islam's divine sovereignty emerged as the most contentious subject in modern Islamic political theory. The predominant argument is that God's sovereignty cannot be compromised in Islam since it is not only an intrinsic feature of Islam as a religion but also an indispensable component of Islam (Ahmad 1942).

A good deal of discussion has also been devoted to the topic in contemporary Islamic political theory. In contrast to Western political theory, which places an emphasis on the individual as the center of the universe, Islamic political theory places God in that position. According to contemporary liberal democratic ideas, sovereignty is one of the key characteristics of the modern nation-state and is a hotly contested topic in Western political tradition. With an analysis of the historical-political background, the current study focuses on the development and emergence of the notion of sovereignty within the school of Modern South Asian Islamic Political thought. However, the development of politics as a fundamental idea in state formation and the emergence of popular sovereignty in Western and Islamic Political Thought may be seen in the history of political concepts. Both the Islamic and Western traditions have considerably more heated discussions over how the idea of sovereignty has evolved. Islam bases its notion of sovereignty on the union of politics and religion. While, in the Christianity or Western Political tradition the premise of sovereignty is based upon the popular opinion of the people, meaning a sovereign body or the council of the Supreme, that goes through the different processes of Historical transformation over the decades. Each period in Western thought consists of a different context for the development of sovereignty. From an Authority-based monarchical sovereign state to the King, then a rivalry of Church-state separation to the people as sovereign authority. The Concept of Sovereignty has gone through different stages of evolution in Western political tradition. Islamic traditions that started from the time of the Prophet have different attributes of Sovereignty but the commonality in the thought of each period is that they Claim God as

the Supreme ruler on the earth in which people have no space, but that consists of the different unfolding of authorities of execution which became a mode of practicing of God's command, like the Caliph or Emir considered of the vicegerent of God. While the latest Islamist political tradition of thought Gives a Political account of Sovereignty in Islam that reduced the religious essence of authority only to a Political one, like Mawdudi and Syed Qutb. The latest Islamist debate is surrounded by a reductionist approach to defining Sovereignty that considered God as the only owner and king of the land and establishing God's rule on this earth is the supreme purpose of the faithful. Syed Abul Ala Maududi (father of Islamists ideologues) and Hifzurrahman Seoharvi and Ali Miya Nadwi were highly influential in shaping Deobandi's position, on principles related to the political nature of Islamic theology), Maududi affirmed sovereignty as an attribute of God, and the rulers as subservient to God's will, while, Seoharvi suggests that God's sovereignty does not entail that the caliph or Amir cannot be a ruler or hakim, nor can his command or Hukum be an order. Certain references have also been made to contemporary scholars like Syed Qutb, and Rashid al Ghannouchi, who in one way or another other have contributed to the debate on 'sovereignty in Islamic thought'. Even Nadwi criticizes the Mawdudi for taking a merely political look at sovereignty and portraying it as the mere purpose of Islam to establish divine sovereignty for the removal of all Muslim problems. But, the most striking question regarding sovereignty that comes to our mind in today's discussion is whether this concept still has the value of what it is known for. In our current conversation, the most interesting topic about sovereignty is whether it now holds the same importance as what it formerly did. In particular, the ancillary question of whether sovereignty is an indivisible, divvy-up, or abstract form of authority falls within the umbrella of the what-it-is debate. In particular, the question of who holds it raises the related issues of whether it belongs to an individual or a group, and whether ownership and use must coexist or can be divided. However, these queries did not include sovereignty in and of itself. The contested character of sovereignty and its meaning do not allow for the prospect of excluding the more traditional forms of government. These questions did not, however, extend to sovereignty in and of itself. The contestation in the meaning of sovereignty and its changing nature does not leave any space for the possibility to rule out the older idea and rethinking it in a

new direction. This possibility cannot be ruled out. The concept of sovereignty did not possess from the very start the central role it has held until recently. It owes its central role to a very particular historical constellation and is thus not immune to loss of meaning if this constellation disappears. The purpose of this paper is to focus on the Western ontological differentiation while comparing it with the Islamic tradition of Sovereignty, while the new challenges met by the Modern Islamists from within through other Islamic Scholar like Hifzur Rahman Seoharvi, like most of the time I will be focusing on the debate of the Islamists Sovereign Idea particularly Mawdudi and its Divergences that take its root from within through the reflection of a great Deobandi Scholar Maulana Hifzurrahman Seoharvi and Ali Miya Nadwi.

The Idea of Divine Sovereignty in Islam

In Islam, of sovereignty within the Islamic State, where ultimate authority is believed to rest with God alone. In this context, Islamic law, or Sharia, is seen as the embodiment of God's will and commands, guiding moral, legal, and religious principles for the Muslim community (Kamali 1989). Given that divine revelation ceased with the passing of the Prophet Muhammad, understanding God's will is primarily sought through the Qur'an and the authentic Sunnah (Ibid). Ilyas Ahmad, the legal aspect of Islam recognizes the sovereignty of Allah. The word sovereign in Islam could be used only for Allah. The contestation lies at various levels due to its executive location such as it involves various levels, including the Sovereignty of Allah, the Holy Quran, the prophet's Sovereignty, Khulafāh, Kings and Emperors even the state (Ahmad 1958, p. 244).

“Behold, thy Lord said to the angels: "I will create a vicegerent [Khalifa (caliph)] on earth.” They said: "Wilt Thou place therein one who will make mischief therein and shed blood? whilst we do celebrate Thy praises and glorify Thy holy (name)?" He said: "I know what ye know not.” (Qur'an 2:30) (March 2013, p.293).

The idea of sovereignty in Islam covers a long period of evolution over different decades. But the question is that what it means of God's sovereignty and from where all such concepts were derived. Let us discuss it from the controversy that started earlier after the prophetic period.

The assassination of 'Ali and the emergence of the Kharijites indeed reflect a significant moment in Islamic history, highlighting the complex interplay between political power, religious authority, and the interpretation of Islamic principles. The Kharijites' rejection of 'Ali's decision to arbitrate with Mu'awiyya stemmed from their uncompromising belief in the absolute sovereignty of God (Allah) (March 2013). For them, any human authority or arbitration conflicted with the principle that ultimate authority rests solely with Allah. This belief led them to view 'Ali's acceptance of arbitration as a betrayal of divine sovereignty, despite his esteemed position as the rightful Imam of the Muslim community (Ibid).

The Kharijites' adherence to this principle also meant that they were willing to challenge even established religious and political authorities, including Ali (R.A.) himself. This uncompromising stance often brought them into conflict with mainstream Islamic authorities of their time. While the Sunni-Shi'a split did not originate contemporaneously with the events surrounding 'Ali's assassination, these events did contribute to the emergence of distinct theological and political factions within Islam. The Kharijites, with their fervent belief in the absolute sovereignty of God, represent one such faction that played a significant role in shaping Islamic history and thought (Ibid 296). In summary, the assassination of 'Ali and the emergence of the Kharijites serves as a poignant reminder of the complex dynamics of power, authority, and ideology within the early Muslim community, highlighting the diverse interpretations of Islamic principles and their implications for political and religious leadership.

Sovereignty in Western Political Traditions: Metaphysics and Ontological Identity

In Western tradition or Christianity, religion and politics were kept distinct, which influenced the transfer of sovereignty from God to the king and eventually the king to the people. The theoretical foundations of sovereignty in Islamic tradition and Western tradition are quite different. Although God was granted ultimate authority in the beginning or early times, temporal leaders were not permitted to exercise absolute power over the populace. In the late Middle Ages, this idea of sovereignty got challenged, and rulers started to claim the supreme authority and give this claim legitimacy through sources of God and

People. This model of sovereignty is entitled to the “regionalist model” of sovereignty, where the king was the only supreme authority. In Western tradition protestant reformation laid the foundation of popular sovereignty, in opposition to it, In Islam never found such transformation, rather Islam does not provide space for the separation of religion and Politics, there was no central authority in Islam where it needed to separate like in Christendom, however, this theses of Islam got challenged by many where they discussed that Islam’s engagement with politics was diverse, and there are so many instances where politics get separated from religion. Where politics got a temporal entitlement in Western thought or tradition, In Islam positions regarding the separation of religion and politics are diverse, since the time of the prophet the political status of Christianity and Islam was different from what I did (Brown, 2000). If we look into the meaning of sovereignty, it’s not easy to keep ourselves limited or define it in just an abstract manner in the words of Hinsley, In other words, he defines it in the long term or for longer than there is the ultimate and unquestionable authority in the political community: "Sovereignty is not a fact, It is a concept that men in certain circumstances have applied- a quality they have attributed or a claim they have countered-to the political power which they or other men were exercising" (Hinsley, 1986 pp.1-5). In the Western history of political thought, this word got an intense imagination whereby many thinkers attributed it in a different sense, according to Laski it was an unimaginable task to separate the church and state in the medieval period, eventually, if we discuss that, was there any imagination of sovereignty or supreme authority? he quotes or draws a projection in which he concluded the two great schools were seeking unity through the clash of empire and papacy, but it was broken down before the emergence of nationalities on the one hand and degeneration of Rome on another hand, similarly, all the churchmen by going through the conciliar movement, came with a strong sense for the prerogative or exclusive entitlement for Rome as the mistress of the Christian world, which affirm a sense of sovereignty in middle ages, though a territorial sense of it, was not developed yet (Laski, 2014, p.16). During the development of medieval political theory, the quest for a perfect society was necessary to determine the separate entitlement to both society and the State. It is the term “Sovereignty” that laid the foundation for the same quest, Sovereignty worked as a central inspiring motif that limits the boundary

of an institution which means it created a profound clarity regarding the State as a different entity from other institutions. This foundation attributes to the specialty or outlines the crucial happenings of the Middle Ages (d'Entreves,1967, p.89). The development of Sovereignty was a requirement in the context of the development of the Middle Ages, in order to do so, those two institutions played a consolidated role, one is, "the representation like a constitutional device by means of which the 'approval' of the community, required to make law valid, could find the clear and positive expression" (d'Entreves,1967 p. 90). Sovereignty has been a crucial idea in political and legal discourse for millennia. This does not imply that it has always been clear what it means or even that it has been the same. Since the thirteenth century, it has always had some connection to political authority. But in the eight hundred years that followed, political structures underwent such profound transformation that the idea of sovereignty was no longer untouched. It was repeatedly compelled to adjust to the significant shifts in the evolution of political rule. As a result, quite a few aspects of the notion of sovereignty have evolved in meaning over time, therefore the continued usage of the term does not indicate that its meaning or source remains constant. Due to its French origins and growing popularity, sovereignty first appeared outside of its place of origin in the late sixteenth century. It has so far encountered a variety of political contexts and intellectual traditions. Its disputed meaning was the result of that. Despite being very appealing, the concept could only be used in many situations if its meaning was changed. Because of this, sovereignty cannot be said to have a timeless, universal meaning. Instead, it might be believed that its composition varies depending on the nation. The sixteenth-century religious schism was the major development. Due to the tough situation being brought under the medieval order, a new form of political rule was established. This new form of political rule varied from its predecessor by consolidating and enhancing the powers of the ruler which parallelly limited their rule of territory, Jean Bodin added these characteristics to the concept of sovereignty and thus lent it new, extraordinarily potent significance. Soon, it became clear that a political arrangement with these features was a "state." State formation became the era's resounding theme, and all monarchs shared a desire for statehood. The universal Christian world order accommodated particularistic nations that coexisted side by side, identified themselves by their claims to

sovereignty, and governed their interactions on that basis as state formation developed. Thus, sovereignty gained an internal and an exterior dimension, but also a meeting point with the right to self-determination. Only if the state was free from heteronomy in its exterior affairs could it exercise self-determination over its internal affairs. The territorial feature of Sovereignty is an inescapable idea that is a component of the modern state, even the concept of state is the offspring of particular historical circumstances (Laski,2008, p.1). Continuous linkage of the state with the sovereign body which is recognized as the most prominent body of the modern state is a necessary corollary of modern development in politics. Sovereignty means there is a final authority over the public, a superior being to all other people in the state is called a Sovereign. The metaphysics of Sovereignty described by Hallaq in his *Magnum Opus* belongs to Europe, its identity is European in nature, produced by particular situations, particularly the French and American revolutions in the Modern sense. To keep away enslaving the person or a body of people from the tyrant or any kind of authoritarian authority, it was necessary to construct sovereignty in a people sense (means keeping its orientation towards people as the determinant factor in any kind of decision-making (Hallaq,2013p.25). As a result of the development of the Modern State in Europe in the seventeenth century, sovereignty came into existence. While this paints a different picture, in the Middle Ages, princes, kings, and emperors recognized God as the "King of Kings" and the Papacy as superior to themselves (Heywood,2004p.90). Even there was a distinction between earthly and heavenly power. The power of international organizations like the Catholic Church and the Holy Roman Empire was superseded by that of Centralised Monarchies in the fifteenth and sixteenth centuries, along with the blurring of feudalism. While it was envisioned differently in various locations, the Tudor dynasty in England, the Bourbons in France, the Habsburgs in Spain, etc., were all responsible for realizing it. Secular rulers were able to assert their supreme authority for the first time, and they did so using a new vocabulary of sovereignty (Heywood,2009 p.90). First, it was endorsed through Kings, then rulers, and finally converted as a universal Idea through people's consent i.e., popular sovereignty, and then it became visualized as an idea of practice. It is an expedient idea worked out by kings, other rulers, and their representatives and agents, that emerged in the context of European

religious, Political, and Civil war (Jackson,2007 p. 11). Along with that, the rulers of early modern Europe, in the beginning, dug out the idea in contrast to an overarching authority of the pope, in which the pope was the theocratic head of Latin Christendom (Jackson, 2007 p.11). The concept of sovereignty was first developed by certain political and religious figures in medieval Europe who wanted to assert their independence from the papal and imperial authority as well as from one another (Jackson, 2007 p.6). When called to mind, most of the European states in the latter half of the 17th century were not without exception dynastic. They were receiving assistance from the landowner class, which benefited from agriculture and passed on its money through inheritance rights. Although the Westphalian treaty (1648) abolished a significant source of conflict and instability—religion—it did not put an end to disputes over the state's major source of income and riches, which was territorial control and the surplus value produced by farming (Strange,1999 p.2).

Theorizing Sovereignty in Islamists Thought: Quest for “Divine Sovereignty” (Hakimiyah)

Hakimiyah is an Arabic term, which is a verbal noun taking its root from ‘*h.k.m.*’ through this the term ‘*hukm*’ is derived against the ‘*hakim*’ and ‘*hukkam*’, According to Ibn Durayd hakim is entitled to judicial authority, that is also called as ruler or government, according to him God means, Allah is the highest authority, the final ruler or supreme authority (Khatib 2002). This perspective on absolute power and authority is unmistakably contemporary. The word Qutb uses to describe *hakimiyah* is a neologism even though it is derived from the word *hukm*, which is typically translated as "authority" or "judgment." Second, Qutb does have sovereignty as a political idea in mind when he refers to God as the exclusive location and source of all power, Islamist concepts of the state, the law, and Islam itself are all based on this belief of God's sovereignty (Zaman, 2014). The very idea of Divine Sovereignty in Islam was sought after in the 1920s, In demand of exclusive legislation of God (Hakimiyah). In Modern Islamic thought sovereignty derived its meaning largely from the Quran, which means God is the Final authority in Islam the way it is related to language can be traced in two terms one is *al-Mulk* and another one is *Hakimiyah* (Khatab 2010, p.1). In the dictionary the term *malik* denotes the sovereign and is attributed among

the ninety-nine names of Allah, he is the owner of both the temporal and spiritual world, and sovereignty is derived from the word *hakim* which means the supreme judge (Khatb 2006, p.18). The Sunni Islamist movements were started in the wake of the same objective, and the central objective of these movements was to establish God's sovereignty (March 2019, p.76). Abul A'la Mawdudi's *hakimiyyat-ila-hiyya*, which was developed and evolved over the period of six decades of writing and activism, provided the most systematic articulation of the idea of divine sovereignty in the twentieth century. Although Mawdudi may not have been the first to use the phrase *hakimiyyat-ila-hiyya* his ideas have spread extensively enough, to have profoundly influenced the popular imagination in many countries with a majority Muslim population (Zaman 2014, p.394). One of the main tenets of Islamist theory has been the idea of divine sovereignty (*hakimiyah*), originally conceptualized by Mawdudi and later popularised in the Arab world by Sayyid Qutb. Mawdudi and Qutb translate the cosmos, more as being fundamental to the ethos of an Islamic polity and define *hakimiyah* as such as legal and Political (March; Scharbrodt; Khatb 2019 & 2010, p.278). Andrew March called this vision of Mawdudi and Qutb “high utopian Islamism”, in the sequence of formulating /theorizing it, it is Mawdudi, Qutub, and the very latest Rashid Ghannouchi who took a shift from the Mawdudi and Qutb while making the democracy and Islam compatible (March 2019, p.75). Hasan al Banna the founder of the Islamic movement in Egypt also subscribed to the idea of Divine Sovereignty, but, however, he did not theorize it, while on the other hand, Mawdudi maintained a theoretical discourse on the sovereignty of God, a more extremist step followed by Qutb who accepted the idea in a more vigorous way and Ghannouchi argued for the Sovereignty of *Ummah* (Rahman, 2019, p.7-8). According to Muhammad Asad, a scholar of Islam, "People once accept Islam as a divine ordinance, there can be no question of their being endowed with sovereignty in their own right" (Rahman 2019, Asad 1961). Asad denied any vision for people's sovereignty. He adopted the same stance as Mawdudi and Qutb, who believed that God's will, as stated in the Shariah laws, is the source of all sovereignty (Asad, 1961). Islam rejects popular rule that is not in line with the Faith. Islam is a monotheistic religion that sees life as an act of worship in its entirety. It establishes a religious code that governs all aspects of life and does not separate politics from religion or public life from private life.

Islam defines democracy as popular power that is in conformity with sharia, or divine law, rather than as absolute popular power (Turabi 1987, 63–4, 67). The right to rule gives rise to the power to enact laws, the right to dictate how people should live, and the right to establish the principles upon which this life is to be built. Whoever asserts they have the authority to enact laws Hence, life for a people asserts divine dominion over them because he wants to take the most significant aspect of divinity. Whoever among the people accepts this assertion has so chosen to replace the genuine God with this person because he gives to him the most crucial aspects of divinity. (Zayd 1994, p.105, cited by Qutb). Qutb does not believe in multifaceted, multicultural sovereignty. Instead, it is quite explicit and definite. According to God's last revelation, which is made known in the Qur'an, hakimiyah is a direct, all-encompassing, and unchangeable form of Divine Sovereignty that should be applied to all areas of existence. There is no analogy to sovereignty, and it is not ambiguous. It is a quality of the Creator that both upholds and structures the entire history of His creation. To a great extent, Qutbian sovereignty is monolithic. In the realm of men, only the voice of God's Sovereignty has the right to speak. Qutb makes the ruler, whether a king, president, or member of parliament, solely an instrument of God's Sovereignty with a very small amount of space for normative content, ensuring that the tension between embodied and impersonal sovereignty is eliminated. The idea of the sovereign demos is utterly eliminated, and there is rarely any room for the impersonal sovereignty of the office bearer. Both state sovereignty and popular sovereignty are categorically rejected by Qutb as distorted forms of divine sovereignty created by a modernity that has lost its transcendent axis. According to Qutb, there is no conflict between a sovereign nation and a sovereign individual subject (Stoica 2017, p.). But if we look into the context, which means the condition in which Qutb formulated his theory on Divine sovereignty, it was his analysis of epistemological defects in Western ideologies like nationalism, secularism, and capitalism that was making space in religion and politics not only space or gap but ultimately it was a clear refusal of God's exclusive sovereignty that he considered shirk and equated it with the period of Jahiliya(Muslim cultures have actually largely disappeared from the planet, despite their superiority complex, fundamental formality, and refusal to accept self-critique: "The Muslim community perished at the moment the rules of

God became suspended on earth." Here, we can see how fundamental Hakimiyah is to Qutb's philosophy. The sole standard that continues to ensure the legitimacy of Islam at both the personal and societal levels is God's Sovereignty, seen in its most literal sense as the only law that structures the praxis of Muslim cultures. The most powerful normative idea in Qutb's political theology is hakimiyah. No tradition, history, institution, or degree of piety can prevent Muslim societies from falling into a catastrophic state of collapse in the absence of a total and universal recognition of God's Sovereignty over all domains of life (Qutb, 1978, p.101).

The Premise of Mawdudi's "Divine Sovereignty or Hakimiyah": A Contextual Analysis

For a Muslim, the Sharia, or the law of God, serves as the cornerstone around which all discussions of politics are built. It signifies absolute good and is theoretically both pre-existing and eternal. It comes before the state and the community (Esposito & Voll, 2016, p. 6-7). The Community serves as a witness for God in the midst of the evil in this world, and the main duty of its government is to carry out the Law. Therefore, the question of why the state exists is not addressed in any Muslim political theory of the state. The premise is that God determines and exposes rights and obligations, and as a result, He—or the divine law—reveals God as the ultimate sovereign (Lambton, 2013, p.1). Similarly, Sovereignty is a contentious topic in Islamic political theory in terms of theoretical interpretation and its politicization Mawdudi comes first, as he interpreted God's sovereignty in a purely religious sense and he did it mostly in the influence of his contemporary political subjugation of Muslims across the world and in wake of nationalist's danger for the protection of Muslims values and culture (Jackson, 2011 p.6). Some questions that we could raise here, one among them is, why Mawdudi was so stubborn towards the religious entrenchment of politics? particularly in this specific time period belongs to the early twenties. We can draw several obvious reasons but some accuracy in terms of context is very much needed to understand the dynamics of the Mawdudian paradigm of Divine sovereignty, we can't see his emphasis on divine sovereignty in the separation of this particular historical-political context which became the premise of Mawdudi's divine sovereignty. Mawdudi had a vision of Islamic revivalism, due to the

Muslim's pathetic condition across the world, like the disintegration of the ottoman empire into oblivion, a favorable condition for the West in the world, condition of political subjugation of Muslims, including intellectual and cultural stagnation of Muslims played an important role in shaping Mawdudi's religious orientation of politics and as a counter figure (Ahmad & Ansari,1979 p.361). The list of causes could be expanded to include things like the failure of nationalist secularism, a lack of political engagement, the effects of modernism, a lack of intellectual advancement, etc. I won't go into depth about these reasons because, for many Muslims, they come as a natural consequence of the following reason: Muslim countries have strayed from God's intended course which is *Sīrat-e-mustaqueem* (Straight path followed by god's command) (Ataman, 2015 p. 65). Turning to the Qur'an and the Prophet's Sunnah is the only means of eradicating this pandemic. That is how Mawdudi thought about the revival of Muslims' legacy through the establishment of *Hakimiyah* or Divine Sovereignty in the wake of Muslims' pathetic condition and dominance of Western ideologies (Jackson 2011, 80-88). So Mawdudi was in search of a counter-narrative he went through a theoretical propagation of Islamic Polity, among this, the Sovereignty of the divine get more priority in his thought, and along with that he misquoted several Qur'anic verses that were not falling in the category of jihad, in his book *Al-Jihad Fil Islam* he wrongly interpreted several verses that he equated with aggressive warmongering and Jihad, even there is nothing like that in Quran to established Islam through aggressive modes like the use of sword or violence, defensive war or *Qital* that prophet describe was just a category of *jihad* or just a meaning of the one aspect of *jihad* which is a struggle against evil for the propagation of good, even in Quran the propagation of peace was categorized as the greater *jihad*. Mawdudi only tried to justify it by brushing aside the meaning of verses for military conquest (Faizurrahman, 2022). In 1924, Since the fall of the caliphate, an important institution of the leadership of Muslim Umma, an intellectual Islamist Political movement was started, based on the assumption that the whole world is living in *Jahiliya*, which means for peace and stability, Muslims need to get back a divine order or divine sovereignty, that was very much skeptical to the modern idea of sovereignty, this belief was heavily propagated by utopian Islamist like Abul Ala Mawdudi, this idea became a pre-eminent condition of legitimacy for all

political, legislative and moral act (March 2019 p.75-80). But, it's not only Mawdudi, Rashid Rida an Egyptian thinker tacitly extracted this idea of divine sovereignty earlier than Mawdudi, my concern is not only to understand the conceptual weaving of it, along with that politicization and erroneous base of the Idea and the contextual analysis in which Mawdudi exaggerated the position of Divine sovereignty in his own way of interpretation of the religious texts (March, 2019 p.22). Before reaching a debate of Sovereignty in modern intellectual Islamic tradition, it is conditional to take a look at contextual/Historical analysis of the political situation in the nineteenth century, while Mawdudi was in contrast with many of the Deobandi scholars like Husain Ahmad Madani, who replied to the jamaat's Amir in a letter where he disclosed the Mawdudi's wrong premise of politicizing the Islam as merely a political thing, where the establishment of the Islamic state is the only way forward for all existing problems of the world including Muslim Ummah. Mawdudi could be divided as young and old, his life has two realities in his younger age he was a staunch supporter of Jamaat-e-Ulma-e Hind (JUH), founded in 1919, In 1920s congress got an alliance with JUH, rather he published the biographies of Hindu leaders like Malviya and M K Gandhi, suddenly he gets to disenchanted with the congress by experiencing the congress nationalism that was in favor of Hindu culture and marginalized the Muslim culture and their status. In 1928 he left for Hyderabad, and deeply indulged in the study of Islam, just to point out the reason for Muslim's decline, one more reason for his dismaying of nationalism was the breakup of the nationalist line of the ottoman empire at the hands of the colonial western empire after this long study of Islam and Muslims decline, he concluded that the corruption for Muslims' decline lies in the practice of unauthentic Islam, that means a corrupted version of Islam, for taking the Islam into the right direction, he became editor of Tarjumanul Quran in 1932, and after the formation of provincial ministries by congress, his ideology became crystal clear, where he equated the ministries policy with “Hindu raj”(Mawdudi, Ahmad & Ansari 1938, 1979 & 2017 p. 360-361). Though he criticized the ministries for keeping Muslims in the second-class category as of their agenda to marginalize them more. For him, Congress did not differentiate between Hindu nationalism and Indian nationalism, where the only policy of Congress was to be anti-muslim, so the fault of Congress in making Hindu nationalism and Indian

nationalism conterminous, this stand drove the Mawdudi towards Theo democracy, for what many of the political scientists, social scientists, philosopher theologize the Mawdudi for his view on Theo democracy (Ahmad, 2017p.86-89). The term *Hakimiyat-ila-iyah* used by Mawdudi, have layers of connotation and its evolution consist of a historical tragedy in different decades of Islamic politics, which allowed it to be different meaning in different contextual analysis, though Mawdudi appeared as a countering figure to refute the modern state sovereignty which does not left any space for faith in politics, The issues he raised about the necessity for moral restraints on state and people sovereignty also touched on issues with colonial, anti-colonial, and neo-colonial impositions in the Muslim world. Mawdudi pushed for acknowledging the role this played in covertly imposing and legitimizing the authority of the state, devoid of any popular consent, by first raising concerns about the potential ethical dangers of the idea of popular sovereignty, which is devoid of any of the moral limit (Iqtedar& Scharbrodt 2022, p. 278).

Critiquing “Divine Sovereignty “or Hakimiyah of Mawdudi: A Reflection through the Hifzur Rehman Seoharvi and Ali Miyan Nadwi’s Thought (A Deobandi Tradition)

It is completely necessary to understand the background of the political history and the context in which Mawdudi’s thoughts evolved, Mawdudi eschewed the traditional and formal religious understanding, rather he shaped his thought in the context of the colonial enmity of Islam and Muslims in India even across the globe, based on his own personal learning of religion and an overwhelming orientation in the direction of to protect Islamic values purported an extremist and revolutionary interpretation of Islam, similarly the idea of sovereignty in Mawdudi’s thought got extremists and exaggerated interpretation and valued more than it entitled in comparison to differentiating or prompting the value of religion and politics in Islam, where Mawdudi laid upon mere political touch to the idea of sovereignty, which is a Schmidtian, not an understanding of Islam about sovereignty, but surely the Islamists one, exclusive of Islam (Gani & Ahmad, 2023 & 2013p. 58-88). Mawlana Mawdudi, the founder of modern Islamists, was a great sympathizer of Hakimiyah, which is a concept of sovereignty in Islam, which consists

that God is the only Sovereign of this universe, and no one is the supreme except the command of Allah. So far we looked at Mawdudi’s imagination of sovereignty, but, other scholars like those who belong to the Deobandi tradition, their discourse on sovereignty is yet to discuss in mainstream politics, except for a few, that we need to discuss in the context of religious scripture, which means the right way to practice the *hakimiyah*, so the question that we can raise here is not about to look at *hakimiyah* as Islamist’s concept but a different tradition on sovereignty dealt by Deobandi scholars like Nadwi and Hifzur Rahman Seoharvi, They criticized Mawdudi and his view on Sovereignty (*Hakimiyah*), so which one is on the right path? Is it Mawdudi or do we need a slight critique of Mawdudi that can be added as an accurate way of understanding sovereignty in South Asian Islamic political thought? For that matter, Roy Jackson, who wrote on Mawdudi and interpreted the colonial context in which Mawdudi was trapped, created a transhistorical Islamist ideological movement. Mawdudi tried to have a colonial critique or he was in favor of taking an extremist ideological view that vehemently criticized the colonial occurrence of *Jahiliya* among Muslims, same was also imitated by Syed Qutb, in his view this occurrence was heavily indebted in the context of colonial atrocities done by Britishers against the Muslims, So what he said “Mawdudi was brought up in the specific historical and social context of India at a time of decline in British colonial power, coupled with a likewise decline in Muslim Mogul dominance and the subsequent rise of Hindu nationalism and secularism(Jackson, 2011, p.88-90). One of the vocal experts on Mawdudi Prof. Humeira Iqtedar described Mawlana Mawdudi as the Founding Father of the Modern concept of the *Hakimiyah*. Along with that, she mentioned how an epistemological contrast of the Modern state gave birth to so many anti-colonial movements at the dawn of acting out of British colonialism in India. She discussed the concept of God’s Sovereignty that Mawdudi inherited in the wake of colonial hegemony about whom Mawdudi looks very entrenched while throwing reflection that Allah’s ownership of the Cosmos as Muhammad the messenger of God (Iqtedar, 2019p. 1-3). Mawdudi was a critique of Ulama, and his ideology was premised upon creating a new community of righteous individuals, those who can lead the people on the right Islamic path and could produce an Islamic revolution. Mawdudi also discussed the domain of sovereign authority in Islam by criticizing ulama that they

have no role in decision-making in his own imagination of an Islamic State, he entitled *Amir* as the authority to work with the consultation of others, but he never envisages a role to ulama in guiding the Islamic state. He considered western educated Muslim intellectuals and Ulama as the impediment to the progress of the Islamic State (Zaman, 2002, p.104). This statement of Mawdudi is contradictory in the context of the sovereignty of God, which means divine law because the idea that only God has the right to command and create laws does not create an order in which divine law works in the unmediated, self-interpreting and self-enforcing way. It has never been an intuitive process in which all commands or edicts are cogent as the application of norms extracted from revelatory text, obviously, there are legal orders that try to further or justify divine sovereignty even those that do not remain (March, 2019 p.18). But the question is how to meditate to uphold the divine sovereignty, why the fundamentalists like Mawdudi considered the ulama as the impediment to the progress of an Islamic state, is there any other way too? or is it implicit that Ulama also falling into the domain of upholding divine sovereignty? This idea is extensively discussed by Usama Al Azami an expert on Islamic studies in which he explored the point of distraction that shaped the Mawdudian conception of Sovereignty in an unmediated divine rule, though we need mediums to uphold the dignity and practice of the deepest sense of divine sovereignty, Azami reflected the Ali Miya Nadwi and Hifzurrahman Seoharvi's views on Mawdudi's conception of Sovereignty as a critique which added the further elaboration of sovereignty and also pointed out the fault with which the Mawdudian discourse of God's sovereignty suffered. Instead of, propagating the unmediated concept of sovereignty, one of the greatest intellectuals of the Islamic religion, Ali Miya Nadwi stayed with Mawdudi but with a different explanation, like, the commands of God could not merely reduce to political projects, like any command other than God is shirk in Mawdudi's view, though Nadwi explained it that several areas of life have been left by God in which god has given autonomy to practice the human wisdom to make the life aesthetic and prosperous (Sikand & Al-Azami 2018 & 2022). Nadwi depicts Mawdudi and Qutub as having identical interpretations of Islam, stating that Qutub was profoundly struck by and in complete agreement" with Mawdudi's concepts. His criticism of these two elder authors, whom he would have regarded as friends and possibly mentors for a

period of his life, can be summed up in two interconnected ways. The first is his worry that Islam is being over-politicized to the point where ex-communication is required. In this sense, Nadwi contends that certain of Mawdudi’s assertions regarding *Hakimiyah* are exaggerated. In order to manifest this, he uses Mawdudi's claim that rejecting God's political power is just as incompatible with Islamic doctrines as rejecting God's ultimate authority, “If someone appreciates the word of someone else,” Mawdudi asserts that "If anyone regards the word of another as deserving of obedience without any sanction from God, he is as guilty of associating partners with God (shirk) as the one who prays to or worships someone apart from God". Similarly, he contends that a ruler who asserts absolute political authority is effectively claiming godhood. These are striking claims, and Nadwi contends that they are contrary to Islamic teachings. It is unquestionably incorrect to view Nadwi's critique of Mawdudi as supporting the full sovereignty of humans over the creation of law. However, he argues that polytheism and the literal worship of deities other than God is a much worse sin in Islam. He believes that whereas the others are a more subtle sort of shirk that is not as blameworthy as the former, these represent pure shirk. In his publications, Mawdudi ignores a distinction that Nadwi is using to support his claim because it is well-established in the Islamic scholarly tradition. *Al-shirk al-akbar* or *al-shirk al-jal* are examples of greater or manifest shirk. *Al-shirk al-as ghar* or *al-shirk al-khafi* are examples of lesser or subtle shirk. The Prophet warns against the lower kind of shirk (*al-shirk al-Asghar*), which he defines as relating to *Riya*, i.e., doing acts of worship dishonestly just so that others may witness one's devotion, in hadiths that allude to the subsequent types of shirk (Al-Azami, 2022 p. 378-381). Nadwi had a clear difference with Mawdudi when Mawdudi strictly declared that those who reject God’s Sovereignty are “ as guilty of the offense of the shirk as the one who prays to worship someone other than God”, Though, Nadwi resented this view, he elaborated that political order cannot be equivalent to polytheism, this comes from the reading of Mawdudi’s ideas on sovereignty that most crucial shirk pertains to the political and legal order, and placed the actual polytheism like the idolatry of secondary importance (Azami, 2022 p. 380). The base that actually created a context for such a kind of wrong proposal by Mawdudi was the overemphasis on the political matter and also on the idea of an Islamic state in the wake of colonial dominance in India that

perpetrated a danger against Indian Muslims and their religion (Ahmad, 2013 p.9-11). Establishing a religious authority in Islam is a prerequisite to the recognition of jurists and Ulama, along with that he recognized that political power was only a mode to get the higher purpose which is seeking the pleasure of God, so, he pointed out that Mawdudi was stuck in the ambiguity of priorities in Islam, the actual priority lies in establishing the religion in a holistic way, through (creedal tenets) *Aqaid*, *Ibadat* (devotional practices), *Muamalat* (transactions) rather than gaining political authority, caliphate, government or sovereignty (Al-azami &Usmani, 2022 &2008, p. 367-174). Hifzur Rahman Seoharvi one more great Deobandi scholar of pre-independence India who was not in support of Pakistan, elaborated his views on the sovereignty of God, in the context of legislative authority in Islam, which Maududi highlights that God is the sole legislator, Seoharvi refused this view and extended that legislative authority belongs to god does not mean that caliph and his associates- those who loosen and bind the public affairs of Muslims, in the language of medieval constitutional theory cannot adapt the law to changing needs, other than this he says, the door to the articulation of new legal norms (Ijtihad) would be barred, which can hardly be the case if the law is to remain receptive to changing needs. But the laws that are to be devised by human beings, he says, are to be framed in light of the fundamentals of God's law and of their underlying principles, which admit of no change (Zaman, 2015p. 403-404).

Conclusion

The conception of Sovereignty in Islam has plenty of debates, particularly Islamism have contributed a radical rehearsal of sovereignty in the early twentieth century in the wake of various Islamist movement, that emerged in the wake of the colonial onslaught on Muslims and their countries, they really betrayed the location of sovereignty in Islamic political thought. And this radical departure from the traditionalist understanding of sovereignty proposed a sense of incompatibility between Western and Islamic conceptions of Sovereignty, instead Deobandi's Ali Miya Nadwi and Hifzurrahman Seoharvi added a sense of compatibility of Western and Islamic ideas of sovereignty, and if not compatibility then some possibility of alignment to western and Islamic

discourse, this critique of Islamic idea of sovereignty from within added a sense of contribution and rich the debate of sovereignty in the sense of Global conception of sovereignty, and restrained itself from a separate debate or alien to the western popular sovereignty, thinking across the tradition will absolutely create a new dimension of adding and making it rich the sovereignty in global discourse.

Note: The author declares that there is no conflict of Interest!

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